

Applications of acidic and basic TSIL in multicomponent reactions[†]

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Abstract : Task specific ionic liquids (TSILs) where a functional group is covalently tethered to the cation or anion (or both) of the ionic liquid, have received increased attention over the last few years. The incorporation of this functionality imbues the ionic liquid with a capacity to behave not only as a reaction medium but also as a catalyst in some reactions. The development of new eco-compatible green methodologies and novel complex structures via combined use of multicomponent reactions (MCRs) and TSILs offers several advantages like high yields, shorter reaction times, simple work up, efficient recovery and recycling of the ionic liquid compared with conventional methods. The present review gives an update of current progresses in the arena of acidic and basic TSILs with emphasis on their applications in MCRs.

Keywords : Task specific ionic liquids, acidic ionic liquids, basic ionic liquids, multicomponent reactions.

Introduction

Ionic liquids (ILs) are salts, composed of ions and are generally liquids below 100 °C. The first reported ionic liquid was ethyl ammonium nitrate which is a liquid at room temperature [m.p. 12 °C]¹. These ionic liquids have several interesting properties such as excellent chemical and thermal stability, non-volatility, non-coordinating nature, good solvating capability, wide liquid range and ease of recycling. Their negligible vapour pressure, conventional non-flammability and outstanding solvation potential are the basis for being classified as “green” solvents². The properties of both the cations and anions can be independently modified in ILs. This has spurred the rise of task specific ionic liquids, or the so-called functionalized ionic liquids³⁻⁵. Task specific ionic liquids (TSIL) have been defined as ionic liquids bearing a functional group covalently tethered to the cation or anion or both³. This concept was introduced by Weirbicki and Davis (Jr.)⁶ in 2000 following the demonstration that a thiazolium IL could interact specifically with a solute and function both as a solvent and a catalyst for the benzoin condensation⁷. Recently several reviews dealing with the application of different classes of TSILs in organic synthesis have been published⁸.

TSILs can be classified on the basis of their application in organic reactions as acidic ionic liquids (Lewis acidic, Bronsted acidic, Bronsted-Lewis combined acidic), basic ionic liquids (Lewis basic, Bronsted basic, Bronsted-Lewis combined basic), ionic liquids containing metallic elements (ionic liquids with an anion or cation containing metal ion), chiral ionic liquids (ionic liquid with chiral cation or anion) and other task specific ionic liquids containing a specific group aimed at meeting the catalytic requirement of some specific organic reactions.

Multicomponent reactions (MCRs) have emerged as a powerful tool for the construction of novel and complex molecular structures due to their advantages over conventional multistep synthesis. The major advantages of MCRs include lower costs, shorter reaction times, high atom-economy, energy saving and easy separations. It has been demonstrated that MCRs are generally environment friendly, and offer rapid access to large compound libraries with diverse functionalities⁹⁻¹². Therefore, combination of MCRs with task specific ionic liquids has emerged as a promising strategy for the development of novel methodologies in organic synthesis involving multiple bond-forming transformations. In this review, we have abridged below some of the recent advances of acidic

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and basic TSILs from the perspective of their application in the multicomponent reactions.

β-Amino carbonyl compounds

Gong *et al.* conducted the three component Mannich-type reaction of ketones, aromatic aldehydes and aromatic amines, catalyzed by 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hydroxide ([Bmim]OH)^{13a}, to prepare various β-amino carbonyl compounds in high yields. TSILs like *N,N,N*-trimethyl-*N*-butanesulfonic acid ammonium hydrogen sulfate ([TMBSA]HSO₄) in water^{13b}, 3-(*N,N*-dimethyldodecylammonium) propanesulfonic hydrogen sulfate ([DDPA]HSO₄)^{13c} and 1-methylimidazolium trifluoroacetate ([Hmim]TFA)^{13d} have also been reported to catalyze this reaction [eq. (1)].

Sahoo *et al.* conducted the same reaction using Bronsted acidic ionic liquids, IL1 and IL2 to afford β-amino carbonyl compounds in excellent yield and short reaction time (Fig. 1)^{13e}.

Fig. 1

β-Acetamido ketones

Synthesis of β-acetamido ketones has been achieved by one pot reaction of acetophenone, aryl aldehydes, acetyl chloride and acetonitrile by using 3-methyl-1-(4-sulfonylbutyl) imidazolium hydrogen sulfate ([Mim-(CH₂)₄SO₃H]HSO₄)^{14a}, or 1-methylimidazolium hydrogen sulfate ([Hmim]HSO₄)^{14b} (TSILs) as catalyst in solvent free media at room temperature [eq. (2)].

Fig. 2

A series of novel bi-SO₃H-functionalized ionic liquids were synthesized and used as catalysts for the synthesis of β-acetamido ketones by Wang *et al.* Compared with traditional single-SO₃H functionalized ionic liquids, lesser amount of catalyst, higher yields of products and shorter reaction time are the key features of these ionic liquids (Fig. 2)¹⁵.

1-Carbamatoalkyl-2-naphthols, 1-amidoalkyl-2-naphthols and 1-thioamidoalkyl-2-naphthols

Condensation of aldehydes, amides and 2-naphthol in presence of a catalytic amount of TSILs like *N*-(4-sulfonic acid) butyl triethylammonium hydrogen sulfate ([TEBSA]HSO₄)¹⁶, 1,3- disulfonic acid imidazolium hy-

drogen sulfate ([Dsim]HSO₄)¹⁷ and triethylamine-bonded sulfonic acid ionic liquid ([Et₃N-SO₃H]Cl)¹⁸ under solvent free conditions afforded corresponding 1-amidoalkyl 2-naphthols [eq. (3)]. Similarly, synthesis of 1-carbama-

toalkyl-2-naphthols by condensation of aldehydes, carbamic esters and 2-naphthol has been reported as catalyzed by ionic liquids ([Dsim]HSO₄)¹⁷ and ([Et₃N-SO₃H]Cl)¹⁸ [eq. (3)].

Synthesis of 1-thioamidoalkyl-2-naphthols was also achieved by Zare *et al.* via reaction of 2-naphthol, aryl aldehydes and thioamides in presence of ([Et₃N-SO₃H]Cl)¹⁸ [eq. (3)].

α -Aminophosphonates

A sulfonic acid functionalized ionic liquid has been used as a Bronsted acid catalyst for the one pot, three component synthesis of α -aminophosphonates from aldehydes/ketones, amines and trimethyl phosphite at room temperature in water [eq. (4)]¹⁹.

Pyrroles

[Bmim]OH, catalyzed three component condensation of acid chlorides, α -amino acids and dialkyl acetylenedicarboxylates in water was reported by Yavari and Kowsari to afford functionalized pyrroles in high yields [eq. (5)]²⁰.

Imidazoles

Khosropour has reported an efficient and environment

friendly procedure for the synthesis of 2,4,5-trisubstituted imidazoles using catalytic amount of [Hmim]HSO₄ in ethanol [eq. (6)]^{21a}. This reaction can also be catalyzed by 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazole acetate ([Emim]OAc) under ultrasonic irradiation^{21b} and by [Mim-(CH₂)₄SO₃H]HSO₄ under solvent free conditions^{21c}.

A four component MCR route from benzil (or benzoin), substituted benzaldehydes, ammonium acetate and phenyl hydrazine has also been reported for the synthesis of 1,2,4,5-tetrasubstituted imidazoles using *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidonium hydrogen sulfate ([NMP]HSO₄) at 100 °C [eq. (7)]^{21d}.

Synthesis of imidazo[1,5-*a*]pyridines was also achieved

by one pot condensation of 1,2-dipyridylketone, aromatic aldehydes and ammonium acetate in [Hbim]BF₄, at 100 °C [eq. (8)]²².

The reaction of phthalhydrazide, aromatic aldehydes and malononitrile using controlled microwave irradiation in the presence of [Bmim]OH at 45 °C allowed facile access to 1*H*-pyrazolo[1,2-*b*]phthalazine-5,10-diones [eq. (9)]²³.

Benzotriazoles

Wang *et al.* have exploited the MCR approach for the synthesis of *N*-(α -alkoxyalkyl)benzotriazoles [eq. (10)] via condensation of benzotriazole, aldehydes and alcohols catalyzed by acidic ionic liquid [Hmim]HSO₄ at room temperature²⁴.

Pyridines and pyrimidines

Davoodnia *et al.* have reported an efficient procedure for the preparation of 2,4,6-triarylpyridines [eq. (11)] by reaction of acetophenones, aryl aldehydes and NH₄OAc

in presence of [Mim-(CH₂)₄SO₃H]HSO₄ which acts both as catalyst and medium²⁵.

Pentasubstituted pyridines could be synthesized by task specific ionic liquids like 2-hydroxyethylammonium ac-

followed by condensation with aldehydes has been reported by Dabiri and co-workers [eq. (17)]³⁰.

Benzoquinazolin-2-one derivatives were synthesized by using TSIL, 1-methyl-3-(4-sulfobutyl)imidazolium-4-methylbenzene sulfonate through a one pot multicomponent Biginelli reaction of α -tetralone, aldehydes and urea/thiourea [eq. (18)]³¹.

1,8-Dioxo-decahydroacridines

[Hmim]TFA^{32a} and Bronsted acidic ionic liquid containing perfluoroalkyl tails either in monomeric or dimeric version (IL)^{32b} catalyzed synthesis of 1,8-dioxo-decahydroacridines has been reported by three component one pot reaction [eq. (19)].

Thiazolidin-4-ones

An expeditious one pot synthesis of 2,3-diaryl/3-

heteroaryl-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones has been accomplished by condensation of heteroaromatic amines, 2-mercaptoacetic acid and aromatic aldehydes in ionic liquids, viz. 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ([Bmim]BF₄) or 1-methoxyethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoroacetate

([Moemim]TFA) [eq. (20)]³³. [Moemim]TFA gave better yield of products probably due to the ability of the former to develop hydrogen bonds with the amines.

Oxazines

Some pyridinium-based functionalized ionic liquids like N-propanesulfonic acid pyridinium hydrogen sulfate

([PSPy]HSO₄), hexafluorophosphate ([PSPy]PF₆), tetrafluoroborate ([PSPy]BF₄), *p*-toluenesulfonate ([PSPy]*p*-TSA) and dihydrogen phosphate ([PSPy]H₂PO₄) were reported as catalysts for the synthesis of 1,2-dihydro-1-arylnaphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazine-3-one derivatives via a multicomponent reaction of 2-naphthol, aromatic aldehydes and urea under solvent free conditions. ([PSPy]HSO₄) was found to be the best catalyst [eq. (21)]³⁴.

Xanthenes

The synthesis of tetrahydrobenzo[*a*]xanthene-11-ones can be carried with catalytic amount of TSILs ([Dsim]HSO₄)^{35a}, ([Mim-(CH₂)₄SO₃H]HSO₄)^{35b} and sulfonic acid functionalized pyridinium chloride ([pyridine-SO₃H]Cl)^{35c} under solvent free conditions and with 1-butane sulfonic acid-3-methylimidazolium tosylate ([Bsmim]Ts)^{35d} under microwave irradiation [eq. (22)].

Khurana *et al.* have reported an efficient synthesis of

dibenzo[*a,i*]xanthene-diones via three component condensation of 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone, aldehydes and 2-naphthol [eq. (23)] using [Bmim]HSO₄ as TSIL. Reactions attempted using 2,6-dihydroxy naphthalene and 2,7-dihydroxy naphthalene instead of 2-naphthol also resulted in the formation of corresponding xanthenes using [Bmim]HSO₄ as catalyst^{35e}.

A series of tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]xanthene-triones have

been synthesised via the condensation of aldehydes, 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone and cyclic 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds like dimedone, cyclohexadione, 5-methyl cyclohexa-1,3-dione, cyclopenta-1,3-dione using [Bmim]HSO₄ as catalyst and reaction media by Khurana *et al.*^{35f}. This condensation can also be catalyzed with (4-sulfobutyl)tris(4-sulfophenyl)phosphonium hydrogen sulfate (BAIL1) and 2-pyrrolidonium hydrogen sulfate (BAIL2)^{35g} [eq. (24)].

and cyclic 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds has been reported by Hongyun *et al.* (eq. 29)^{36j}. Synthesis of spiro-acenaphthylenes can also be achieved by basic ionic liquid ([BDDMA]Cl)^{36k}.

action times, environmentally benign milder reactions, safe operations, simple work up, efficient recovery and recycling of the ionic liquid compared with conventional methods. Thus, combining MCRs with TSILs offer un-

Synthesis of 12-aryl-12*H*-indeno[1,2-*b*]naphtho[3,2-*e*]pyran-5,11,13-triones and 13-aryl-indeno[1,2-*b*]naphtho[1,2-*e*]pyran-12(13*H*)-ones has been described

paralleled advantages and open up interesting eco-compatible green alternatives to more conventional approaches in modern organic synthesis.

by three component reaction of aldehydes, 2*H*-indene-1,3-dione and 2-hydroxynaphthalene-1,4-dione or 2-naphthol, respectively in presence of TSILs triethylammonium hydrogen sulfate ([Et₃NH]HSO₄), 2-pyrrolidonium hydrogen sulfate ([Hnhp]HSO₄), 3-methyl-1-sulfonic acid imidazolium chloride ([Msim]Cl) and ([Hmim]HSO₄) under solvent free conditions [eq. (30)]^{36l}.

We have illustrated through the selected studies reported above in this review, the synergistic use of MCRs and TSILs that allows the development of new methodologies, and novel complex structures. These processes offer several advantages such as high yields, shorter re-

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